

PREVENTION OF BEHAVIORAL DISORDERS IN ADOLESCENTS WITH BEHAVIORAL DISORDER

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of research on the effectiveness of psychocorrection of behavioral disorders in adolescents. Prevention of behavioral disorders is an important task of practical health care and child psychiatry. Art therapy is the most effective way to prevent behavioral disorders in children and adolescents.*

Keywords: *adolescents; psychotherapy; prophylaxis; art therapy.*

Introduction: The prevention of behavioral disorders is one of the main problems of practical healthcare, as it solves problems not only of medical importance, but also of social, pedagogical and legal significance [1, 10]. Deviant behavior, including suicidal behavior, is one of the urgent problems of child and adolescent suicidology [5]. One of the most important risk factors for suicidal behavior in the general population is the suicide of fiction characters popular among children and adolescents (imitative suicide according to the "Werther effect"), celebrities, rock musicians, and athletes [4]. The death and suicide of "idols" can have a strong impact on the younger generation, and as a result, imitative suicide, in the form of a pathocharacterological imitation reaction typical of adolescence. Sedgwick R., Epstein S., Dutta R., Ougrin D. (2019) identified the relationship between the increase in the number of suicides and the propaganda and advertising of suicide in print, online celebrity suicide content [2,14]. According to foreign and Russian researchers, the phenomenon of cluster suicides has been noted in recent decades. This is what is known in the scientific world as an information epidemic of suicides committed by groups of teenagers in a similar way over a short period of time. Cluster suicides occur after detailed media coverage of the circumstances of the deaths of popular people and celebrities, which has a detrimental effect on immature and particularly impressionable teenagers, which is a trigger point in making the final decision to commit suicide. Communities and groups in social networks and messengers of the Internet space provoke flash mobs and group suicides, which are especially susceptible to unformed teenagers [6,13]. Impulsive copycat suicides in children and adolescents are beyond the comprehension of the adult population, in most cases they are considered undervalued and unlikely due to their insignificance and inconsistency [3,8]. In the literature sources of Russian and foreign researchers, it has been established that the development of the risk of suicidal activity is more associated with short temper, impulsivity and aggressive behavior, the presence of hereditary mental illness and alcoholism [5,7]. One of the most important directions of the preventive approach to the prevention of behavioral disorders in children and adolescents is the study of the role of the family and the educational process in the basic unit of society, the identification of dysfunctional and disharmonious families, incorrect types of child-parent relationships [8,9]. Conducting psychotherapeutic intervention in the form of art therapy, creative healing in order to prevent behavioral disorders in children and adolescents is one of the modern approaches to medical and psychological treatment [11,12].

The purpose of the study: to determine the effectiveness of art therapy in adolescents with behavioral disorders as a method of preventing behavioral disorders.

Research material and methods: 65 adolescents aged 7 to 15 years old, 30 boys and 35 girls who were admitted to the sanatorium departments of Tashkent City Children's Neuropsychiatric Center, were selected as the object of the study. The examination card developed by the staff of the Department of Psychiatry included a list of questions to identify predictors of behavioral disorders and covered the entire range of adolescent activities both in the family and in the surrounding micro society. Group art therapy sessions were conducted as an additional stage of treatment against the background of complex pharmacotherapy and sanatorium treatment. The classes were conducted by medical psychologists and psychotherapists during the children's stay in sanatorium treatment. Modern methods of art therapy technologies were used using educational video lessons from the Pinterest application to create creative products.

Results and discussions: When studying the influence of family relationships on the formation of behavioral disorders, family composition, parental leadership styles, types of upbringing, and the family microclimate were taken into account. When interviewing parents and relatives, we found that 70% of the surveyed were raised in complete families. 18% of the surveyed had only one parent, and this family was classified by us as incomplete. Upbringing by relatives (more often by maternal grandmothers) and upbringing outside the family in the presence of parents (in an orphanage, boarding school) was found in 12% of the surveyed children and adolescents. The study of the type of family showed that destructive families prevailed among the surveyed adolescents (54%), ambivalent families took the second place in frequency (33%), the dysfunctional nature of the parental family was registered in 19% of cases. Harmonious family was observed only in 4 (3.6%) adolescents. When studying the parenting style, we found that adolescents were significantly more often raised in families characterized by child abuse and the use of physical punishment (45%). The hypoprotective parenting style was also relatively more common among the surveyed adolescents (30%). Dominant hyperprotection was more often registered in 25% of the surveyed adolescents. Thus, the parenting style had a certain influence on the formation of behavioral disorders in adolescents, with the most prominent role played by parents' abuse of their children with the use of physical and psychological violence. The gender characteristics of behavioral disorders had significant differences. For example, adolescent girls were found to have eating disorders, increased sexual desire, early onset of sexual activity, refusal to attend school, aggression towards younger siblings in the family, and a tendency to self-harming behavior. The boys were prone to aggression, deviant behavior - smoking, occasional alcoholism, minor hooliganism, theft. At the next stage of the study, adolescents underwent group and individual sessions with medical psychologists and psychotherapists for 3 months according to a specially developed rehabilitation program using modern art technologies. Art therapy was chosen as the main method of psychocorrection. Art therapy sessions were conducted in small groups with primary school children - coloring stencils using watercolor paints. Integrative methods of psychocorrective intervention proved to be the most effective, combining several types of sensory integration with the coverage of visual perception, the development of fine locomotor skills, when both watercolor coloring and paper origami figures were used in group classes, as well as mosaic laying out of various seeds and bean seeds on colored stencils. At the next stage, art therapy was carried out using watercolor and gouache - coloring pictures, followed by gluing beans, peas, lentils and rice on them, which contributed to the development of fine locomotor movements.

Teenagers enjoyed performing the tasks of a psychotherapist, actively coloring stencils, then gluing buckwheat seeds onto the finished pictures, beans, peas, rice, this type of art therapy developed the skills of perseverance, concentration, and broadening the horizons of knowledge and ideas about the surrounding reality. After group sessions of art therapy with the help of medical psychologists, adolescents were tested on the Spielberger scale for anxiety levels, which determined a significant decrease in personal and situational anxiety in all adolescents surveyed, which shows the need for this psychocorrective technique among the adolescent population to prevent behavioral disorders. The creativity of children and teenagers was displayed on stands for public viewing and familiarization. The promotion of a healthy lifestyle, the prevention of behavioral disorders, and styles of improper upbringing in disharmonious families were the main areas of family psychotherapy conducted with the parents and guardians of the examined patients. The most successful works were held in a competition, and the winners were awarded with prizes and valuable gifts. All this motivated the children and made them want to participate in group psychotherapy sessions, and developed creative thinking, creativity, and a desire for improvement. Parents visiting their children at the sanatorium could get acquainted with the works of creativity at special exhibitions of exhibits of children's creativity.

Conclusions: thus, art therapy, as a method of preventing behavioral disorders, is important in the comprehensive medical and pedagogical treatment of children and adolescents in order to prevent behavioral disorders and form a harmonious personality.

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